

Dysgeusia Following Intravenous Medication Administration: A Potential Link to Saline Flush in Prefilled Syringes

Keywords: dysgeusia, intravenous medication, saline flush, prefilled syringes, taste disturbance

Abstract:

Patients reporting an unpleasant salty taste following intravenous (IV) medication administration have drawn scientific attention. This phenomenon, known as dysgeusia, is suspected to be caused by the saline flush in commercially available prefilled syringes. This study aims to investigate the relationship between saline flush and dysgeusia in IV medication administration.

Introduction:

Dysgeusia, a distortion in taste perception, has been reported by patients following IV medication administration. The Norwegian Radium Hospital hypothesized that this effect may be linked to the saline flush used in prefilled syringes. This study explores the mechanisms behind this phenomenon and compares the incidence of dysgeusia between prefilled saline syringes and traditional saline for injection.

Methods:

A randomized, controlled trial was conducted with 10 healthy volunteers. Participants received injections of varying volumes and speeds using both commercially available prefilled saline syringes and traditional saline for injection. Taste and smell disturbances were recorded after each injection.

Results:

Out of 15 recordings, only 2 demonstrated unpleasant tastes or smells with traditional saline injection. In contrast, 14 out of 15 recordings reported taste and smell disturbances with prefilled syringes. The higher incidence of dysgeusia with prefilled syringes is attributed to the release of sodium chloride electrolytes during exhalation.

Discussion:

The mechanism behind this phenomenon likely involves the evaporation of the saline solution into the lungs after mixing with blood, followed by exhalation. This process allows for the perception of taste and smell sensations similar to how exhaled breath can be tasted or smelled.

Conclusion:

While prefilled syringes offer benefits in terms of preparation time and infection control, healthcare professionals should be aware of the potential for dysgeusia. This minor inconvenience should be weighed against the advantages of prefilled syringes in clinical practice.

Sources

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